

MOBIS

MOBILE OBSERVATION INTEGRATION SERVICE

Training & capacity building resources

Cos4Cloud Services

About the MOBIS system & user guide

This is a system and user handbook for [MOBIS](#), a service that provides integrative citizen science mobile applications through which users can report environmental and biodiversity observations using one Android or iOS App.

Description

This is a system and user handbook for **MOBIS**, a service that provides integrative citizen science mobile applications in through which users can access to report environmental and biodiversity observations from one place using an Android or iOS App.

MOBIS has been developed by project partner [DDQ Pocket Science](#) as part of [Cos4Cloud](#) a European Horizon 2020 funded project. The Cos4Cloud project has developed [thirteen services](#) boosting citizen science technological services to help increase and improve the quantity and quality of observations.

MOBIS (Mobile Observation Integration Service) provides user-friendly App interface which gathers and presents citizen science data from smartphone sensors and images making them accessible in one place customised to the requirements of scientific or citizen science communities.

Service Coordinator

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Science

Cos4Cloud Coordinator

The following content has been provided to help guide users of this service.

WHAT IS THE MOBIS?

Mobile Observation Integration Service (**MOBIS**), is a service which has a user-friendly interface that provides an integrative citizen science mobile application which users can access to gather data from smartphone sensors and images reporting environmental and biodiversity observations, from one place using an Android or iOS App.

WHO IS THIS SERVICE FOR?

Accessible as both an Android or iOS app, **MOBIS** is a service aimed at developers of citizen science apps and others with some expertise in web technologies. Developers can add new citizen observatories (COs) and sensors to **MOBIS** making the service accessible to different communities of users. A developer can also create a user-friendly app that collects and combines different types of environmental sensor readings as well as biodiversity observations (i.e. images).

This incorporates environmental sensors and biodiversity citizen science platforms, which end users can use to report data. For example: a citizen scientist can use take air-pollution readings (aerosols in the sky) using [iSPEX](#), a smartphone add-on which is one of the CO / DIY devices involved in Cos4Cloud; as well as a picture of lichens using the same app.

This means that this innovative service allows citizen scientists to access a single place to perform a range of citizen science activities rather than using several different apps. Customised to collect and combine all sorts of information i.e. from photographs or from low-cost sensors, depending on the needs/wishes of the scientific and citizen science communities. This means you can log in once and access a menu to report any environmental or biodiversity data.

WHAT ARE THE BENEFITS OF THIS SERVICE?

Pocket Science focuses on pollution and fostering environmental sustainability through innovative citizen science apps and cutting-edge sensors. Empowering individuals to actively engage in scientific research, contribute to important discoveries, towards impacting on planetary health services align with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, enabling communities worldwide to monitor and tackle air, water, and light pollution in local environments.

Developed as part of this, **MOBIS** provides innovation for new citizen observatories, including:

- A user-friendly interface that can be of both scientific value and provide user feedback.
- Support to develop an app that can gather data on multiple variables, for example, a researcher interested in studying how pollution affects plant biodiversity can develop an app for users to report this data and then analyse it outside the app.
- Access to a system with the capability to store and capture all kinds of data (air, water, images of plants) even offline!

HOW DOES IT WORK?

By integrating **MOBIS** a citizen observatory team developing a new app can utilise powerful and advanced sensors accessible using smartphones. Apps can be used to measure different variables i.e. light, movements and locations. With a common codebase to interface with standardized backend services and open-source technologies, **MOBIS** aims to combine sensor and user data (bearing in mind user privacy), connecting asynchronous mobile frontend and backend for direct interaction distributing datasets for immediate feedback to the user and further analysis by scientists. **MOBIS** offers:

Secure log in: **MOBIS** uses Authenix, a user registration service that guarantees GDPR compliance when logging into the app. This way, users only have to log in once and their privacy and data security are always respected.

Personalisation citizen science apps: a developer or a researcher interested in measuring water quality and getting air-quality readings for research, will be able to use one app to collect this data instead of using several apps.

Saves time: anyone interested in developing a citizen science app can use **MOBIS** to support their user communities and benefit from:

- Logging in just once
- Choose which environmental or biodiversity data they would like to report
- Store observations (air, water, images) offline and upload them later

Sensor integration: **MOBIS** can facilitate the integration of sensors and CO apps, including the [Cos4Cloud COs](#) and [DIY initiatives](#), such as:

- **CanAirIO**: a low-cost sensor device to measure air quality
- **iSPEX**: a sensor to measure aerosols and water colour (pollution indicators)
- **KdUINO**: a buoy with sensors that measure water transparency (a pollution indicator)
- **Pl@ntNet**: a citizen science platform for collecting plant observations

This enables citizen scientists to upload and collect all data in one place. See examples of [user cases](#).

HOW TO USE MOBIS - A STEP BY STEP GUIDE

MOBIS is described “as an all-in-one Mobile Observation Integration System that brings together various citizen science apps for effortless access and convenience”.

Developers can App developers can easily integrate **MOBIS** (<https://pocket.science/products/mobis>) into their projects with the use of the [documentation](#) and [open-source libraries and tools](#) provided.

An open-source citizen science software framework, it allows app developers and researchers to easily integrate air and water quality monitoring, as well as biodiversity research, into their own apps.

MOBIS Integration includes:

- A front-end (client side) service framework
- A back-end (server) serviceLog-in, set up a user profile and explore activity:

MOBIS DOCUMENTATION:

Go to: https://github.com/Pocket-science/MOBIS_PUBLIC which includes information on the **MOBIS** software and documentation. Please note: this is still under development therefore the content is subject to change. The software is developed using a Parse Server (back-end) and the IONIC framework (front-end) (see more below).

MOBIS BACK-END TESTING ENVIRONMENT:

- The MOBIS testing server sits on the EGI (IFCA) and consists of an Ubuntu Virtual Machine with Parse Server as the mobile back end and MongoDB for data storage. It also hosts a Fraunhofer Sensor Things API instance.
- All data is stored in the **MOBIS** parse back-end server, an open source framework which can be accessed through REST/JSON calls on this endpoint: <https://mobis.pocket.science/parse/>
- This back-end (server) service allows for participation in a number of research projects and environmental studies through a single user-friendly app on a smartphone.

Below is a sample of the dashboard view: For user convenience we have a sample dashboard that can be used to look up data:

The screenshot shows a Parse Dashboard interface with a table of raw data. The table has the following columns: id, object_id, PKID, ATTTname, record_ID, CDD, output_name, PAS, and Action_ID. The data rows include various sensor readings and timestamps.

id	object_id	PKID	ATTTname	record_ID	CDD	output_name	PAS	Action_ID
16	yE2A49raEt	11.73044236832073	5a58f970-8b0a-373A...	0		("P1", "P25", "16", "...)	0	1642373220
16	wB7yF6b3w	11.139336615490723	85e9ca09-70ea-4366...	0		("P1", "P25", "16", "...)	0	1642373215
16	1VEM83h0E1	11.139336615490723	22a85610-2971-3762...	0		("P1", "P25", "16", "...)	0	1642373210
16	7P9qy2uR2	11.139336615490723	bf61979f-105c-9f58...	0		("P1", "P25", "16", "...)	0	1642373205
16	3v6x25Dvaw	9.93140220428890	8e462e40-e0e7-3965...	0		("P1", "P25", "16", "...)	0	1642373200
16	3Hgp30yey	9.93140220428890	848c4a1c-6a5a-4662...	0		("P1", "P25", "16", "...)	0	1642373195
16	W03y6T607	9.93140220428890	7a70890f-897a-7336...	0		("P1", "P25", "16", "...)	0	1642373190
15	wg5x711R	10.13304315032903	8e4a8a60-2aa7-3f62...	0		("P1", "P25", "15", "...)	0	1642373185
15	Hkzj768W5	10.13304315032903	4a808300-6ac0-e86a...	0		("P1", "P25", "15", "...)	0	1642373180
15	MUXL768W5	11.32622832355273	3c751793-7920-8987...	0		("P1", "P25", "15", "...)	0	1642373175
15	F20wHng65	11.32622832355273	43072150-9002-5096...	0		("P1", "P25", "15", "...)	0	1642373170
14	5abx230R7	(undeclared)	9c7a0943-2490-837a...	0		("P1", "P25", "14", "...)	0	1642373165
11	4QpAMMqJ	(undeclared)	40931f10-2a39-4876...	0		("P1", "P25", "11", "...)	0	1642373065

AUTHENIX INTEGRATION FOR USER LOGIN:

MOBIS also includes features for user login via **AUTHENIX**, a Cos4Cloud user authentication service. This helps to facilitate secure login and ensure interoperability with other Cos4Cloud services. It also makes it easier for researchers and app developers to collect and share data for their projects. For further information go to the **AUTHENIX website** where the **Privacy Policy** and **Terms of use** are available.

MOBIS APPLICATIONS FRONT END

A front-end (client side) service framework is available which includes a set of scripts and plugins for the development of citizen science apps using the **MOBIS** codebase. This facilitates the collection of different types of environmental and biodiversity data i.e. air and water quality, biodiversity etc.

- **MOBIS** uses the Ionic framework (<https://ionicframework.com/>), a free, open-source framework, to develop the front-end of the mobile application, Ionic is used for building mobile applications with web technologies such as HTML, CSS, and JavaScript, is used which allows developers to build cross-platform mobile apps for iOS, Android, and the web with a single codebase.
- The code for **MOBIS** available on GitHub (https://github.com/Pocket-science/MOBIS_PUBLIC) can be used to generate apps for iOS, Android, and the web (limited to Google Chrome).

MOBIS DEMONSTRATION APP

- Sample software includes integration demonstrations with COs and DIY sensors and devices i.e. [CanAirIO](#) (for air quality), [Mini-Secchi](#) (for water quality), and [Pl@ntNet](#) (for biodiversity research); as well as included i.e. Cos4Cloud COs / DIY devices [iSPEX](#), [KDUINO](#) and [Fresh Water Watch](#)).
- The **MOBIS** App also has these integrations etc as plugins. Combined together they can be accessed via a single sign on. See images demonstrating the **MOBIS** App below:

INFORMATION AND FURTHER SUPPORT

Introduction to this Cos4Cloud service: <https://cos4cloud-eosc.eu/services/mobis/>

About MOBIS: <https://pocket.science/products/mobis>

About Pocket Science: <https://pocket.science/>

MOBIS contact: web@pocket.science

Access the MOBIS documentation: <https://zenodo.org/record/7615472#.ZF0cQ3bMLb6>

Access the MOBIS software / documentation repository: https://github.com/Pocket-science/MOBIS_PUBLIC

The MOBIS Framework: <https://zenodo.org/record/7672811#.ZF0dWnbMLb4>

A MOBIS User case video: [Run4Science](#)

Get the Cos4Cloud infographic for this service: [MOBIS infographic](#)

Access this service from the EOSC Marketplace: <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/mobis-mobile-observation-integration-service>

Additional resources: [About the Cos4Cloud Toolbox and Evidence Hub](#)

This system and user guide is a training resource for MOBIS, one of the technological services co-designed by the Cos4Cloud project (<https://cos4cloud-eosc.eu/>). **Title: MOBIS System and User Guide.** Service Coordinator DDQ: Pocket Science. This guide is one of the Training and Capacity Building resources in the Cos4Cloud Toolbox & Evidence Hub developed by the Open University in collaboration with project partners. Contact: cos4cloud-toolbox@open.ac.uk.

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